

Water purification and storage design report

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WP3.3– Water Purification and Storage

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Approved by: Giorgio Boscheri TAS Work Package Leader

Approved by: Paul Zabel DLR Project Leader

List of Authors:

Participant No.	Short name	Author name(s)
6	TAS	Giorgio Boscheri, Rachele Perelli, Giovanni Marchitelli, Thomas Fili

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1 Introduction

This document, deliverable D3.4 for LUWEX project, details design choices of the WPS subsystem. It includes the generation of the subsystem Design Definition and Justification File (including all necessary analyses), the piping and instrumentation diagram, the physical configuration (including the CAD model and clear fluidic/mechanical/electrical interfaces specification), the Development & Verification Plan (including test plan and test procedures), as well as Verification Plan implementation.

1.1 Applicable Documents

[AD1] LUWEX-LSG-WP2.1-D2.1-System Requirements Document_v1.0

1.2 Reference Documents

- [RD1] LUWEX-DLR-WP2.3-D2.3-Preliminary Design Report-v1.0
- [RD2] Flowmeter IFM SM6020 datasheet ([link](#))
- [RD3] Pressure transmitter IFM PT5404 datasheet ([link](#))
- [RD4] Conductive conductivity sensor IFM LDL101 datasheet ([link](#))
- [RD5] Temperature transmitter IFM TA2105 datasheet ([link](#))
- [RD6] Load Cell Pinto Elettronica 5Kg ([link](#))
- [RD7] Pump Fluid-o-Tech GA072 datasheet ([link](#))
- [RD8] Pump driver Moon’s BLD 10-A-S datasheet ([link](#))
- [RD9] Sartorius Sartopore 2 Maxicaps 1 0.45 µm 544-73-06-G-2-x-x-x datasheet ([link](#))
- [RD10] DuPont Filmtech Aqualast 1812-HR datasheet ([link](#))
- [RD11] DuPont AmberTec UP6040 H/OH datasheet ([link](#))
- [RD12] Activated Carbon Camel Carboclean Actisorb M.J. 950 datasheet
- [RD13] Peristaltic Pump Etatron B3-V 1201 datasheet ([link](#))
- [RD14] Pump MARCO Fluidtech 16404113 - UPX-C (24V) datasheet ([link](#))
- [RD15] LUWEX-TAS-WP3.1-D3.1 – Design definition and justification file v0.2
- [RD16] Irfan K. Shah et al., Steam Regeneration of Adsorbents: An Experimental and Technical Review, Chemical Science Transactions, 2013, 2(4), 1078-1088. DOI:10.7598/cst2013.545
- [RD17] Load Cell Transmitter ATO-LCTR-DY510 ([link](#))
- [RD18] Fluke 287 True-RMS Electronics Logging Multimeter ([link](#))

1.3 Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation
BBM	Breadboard Model
HW	Hardware
LIBS	Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy
MF	Microfiltration
PWR	Politechnika Wroclawska
RO	Reverse Osmosis
SWY	Scanway
TAS-I	Thales Alenia Space Italia
TUBS	Technische Universität Braunschweig
TVAC	Thermal Vacuum chamber
WECS	Water Extraction and Capturing subsystem
WPS	Water Purification and Storage subsystem
WUST	Wroclaw University of Science and Technology

2 Consolidated WPS design description and justification

2.1 Concept of operation

LUXWEX Water Purification and Storage subsystem treats water coming from Water Extraction and Capturing Subsystem. Contaminated water extracted from Lunar surface is purified in WPS until it meets electrolysis feed water requirements according to [AD1] Req. 1.6.3 Water quality for electrolysis applications.

As described in [RD1], contaminants are divided into three categories: particulate, organics and inorganics.

A microfiltration membrane is used to remove particulate.

For organics removal, focusing on methanol as a critical contaminant, activated carbons are used. The option of regenerating AC using steam generated by product water is evaluated to reduce subsystem consumables.

Reverse osmosis for inorganics removal is chosen because of the high removal efficiency of all the present species, especially for ammonia, without the use of consumables. Ion exchange resins are used for final polishing to achieve purity requirement for technical water.

2.2 Design description and justifications

The WPS design is herein described and justified against applicable requirements. All the requirements in this section are identified with respect to [AD1]. See chapter 2.3 for a detailed P&ID of the WPS.

Table 2-1: WPS design features description and justification

Design Feature	Justification
WPS includes multiple steps of liquid water treatment technologies as shown in section 2.3 (i.e. Multi-filtration + Reverse Osmosis + Activated Carbon + Ion Exchange resins). The single water treatment technologies are described in detail in sections from 2.2.3 to 2.2.6	The technologies were selected at the end of a trade-off process documented within D2.3 [RD1]. The selected technologies allow: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - treating water in liquid phase (req. 2.4.1) - achieving target product water quality (req. 2.4.5) - starting from the raw feed water (req. 2.4.3) - consuming less than 1g of consumables per kg of product water (req. 2.4.8). See section 2.2.7 for justification. - potentially achieving target product water to feed ratio >95% (req. 2.4.6). See section 2.2.8 for justification.
WPS includes an inlet and an outlet storage tank (2 L each)	WPS shall work in batch mode and treat from 500 to 1500 mL batches (as per req. 2.4.2).
WPS includes a liquid waste storage tank (0.5 L)	The selected water treatment solution (including RO) produces a concentrated liquid waste stream that needs to be evacuated from the system.
WPS includes a set of sensors and probes, as detailed in chapter 2.2.1.	All sensors and probes are chosen to control the system and to be compliant with req. 1.6.1 Raw water quality monitoring control points and req. 2.4.10 WPS processing parameters monitored. See section 2.2.1 for details.

Design Feature	Justification
WPS includes different type of pumps, as detailed in section 2.2.2.	The overall fluidic design was aimed at guaranteeing a water flowrate > 10 mL/min (as per req. 2.4.4). See section 2.2.2 for more details.
WPS includes a Microfiltration Unit, detailed in section 2.2.3.	Efficient particulate removal without loss of feed water. See section 2.2.3 for more details.
WPS includes a Reverse Osmosis Unit, detailed in section 2.2.4.	Removal of most of the inorganic salts (98-99%) and part of the organic contaminants without the use of consumables. See section 2.2.4 for more details.
WPS includes an Activated Carbon Unit, detailed in section 2.2.5.	Removal of residual organic contaminants to the required product water level without loss of feed water. See section 2.2.5 for more details.
WPS includes an Ion Exchange Resins Unit, detailed in section 2.2.6.	Removal of residual inorganic contaminants to the required product water level without loss of feed water. See section 2.2.6 for more details.
WPS fluidic lines (tubing and fittings) are made of the following materials: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stainless steel • PTFE • Polypropylene • Acetate 	Materials shall be compatible with the raw feed water (req. 2.4.3) and the product water (req. 2.4.5) qualities.
WPS includes 5 sampling ports after technologies as described in section 4.1.	Sampling port are placed in strategic points of the subsystem as required in Req. 2.4.14. They allow water sampling in order to evaluate the proper functioning of the technologies during test phase and if needed during regular function. Sample collected can be tested for EC, pH and TOC.
WPS breadboard is designed to be assembled with other subsystems in TUBS facility outside TVAC chamber.	WPS breadboard works in laboratory environment t with ambient temperature 22+/-5 °C and relative humidity 30 – 50% as required in Req. 1.5.4 and 1.5.5.

2.2.1 Sensors and Probes

Table 2-2: Sensors and probes design features description and justification

Design Feature	Justification
Flowmeter IFM SM6020 [RD2] is placed downstream the RO unit concentrate outlet.	Measuring range: 0.05 – 35 L/min, compatible with the selected RO module expected concentrate flow rate (slightly below maximum feed flow rate of 7.6 L/min). Analog output version was selected as preferred by Data Acquisition and Control subsystem.
Flowmeters IFM SM6020 [RD2] is placed downstream the RO unit permeate outlet.	Measurement range of 0.05 – 35 L/min is compatible with the permeate flowrate of 0.2 L/min. Analog output version was selected as preferred by Data Acquisition and Control subsystem.
Pressure sensors IFM PT5404 [RD3] are placed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - before and after MF unit to evaluate filter clogging, - After P003 to monitor RO pressure increasing and to stop concentrate recirculation when necessary, - After RO unit to monitor the pressure of RO permeate that needs to go to AC and ion exchange resins unit. 	Measuring range: 0 – 10 bar. Operative pressure in the system is expected to be ≈1 bar (ambient pressure). In RO unit, operative pressure is expected to be ≈ 4 bar, max operative pressure of RO membrane is 10 bar. This means that 10 bar will never be overcome in the system. Analog output version was selected as preferred by Data Acquisition and Control subsystem.
Conductivity probes IFM LDL101 [RD4] are placed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - before MF units, measures conductivity of feed mixed with concentrate before entering RO - after RO unit to monitor RO salt reduction 	Measuring range: 0.04 – 1000 μS/cm as Req. 1.6.3 requires <0.056 μS/cm and the max value expected is 300 μS/cm. Analog output version was selected as preferred by Data Acquisition and Control subsystem
Water tank level sensors (custom designed load cells [RD6] + transmitter [RD17]) placed to measure level of water inside inlet and outlet tanks.	Easiest way to measure water level in the tanks (compared to other level sensors). Measuring range: 0 – 5000 g. Max water weight is 1500 g and bottle weight is c.a. 1000 g. Resolution: 20 g. Analog output version was selected as preferred by Data Acquisition and Control subsystem
Temperature indicator IFM TA2105 [RD5] is placed on RO concentrate flow to monitor temperature increase that may damage RO membrane.	Measuring range: -50 – 50 °C. Expected temperature between ambient T and 45°C (RO max operative temperature) Analog output version was selected as preferred by Data Acquisition and Control subsystem

2.2.2 Pumps

Table 2-3: Pumps design features description and justification

Design Feature	Justification
P001 peristaltic pump Etatron B3-V 1201 (PBV4337374) (24VDC) [RD13] is used to pump raw water from the WECS reservoirs to WPS reservoir. The pump provides an adjustable flow rate of until 200 ml/min.	Pump flow rate was selected to be able to move up to 1.5 liters of water within 30 minutes. Pump pressure was selected considering that the WECS reservoir is placed about 2 m below the WPS reservoir.
P002 volumetric pump MARCO Fluidtech UPX-C (24V) [RD14] is placed upstream the multi-filtration bed. The pump provides a max pressure of 2 bar.	Pump pressure was identified to overcome MF ΔP and avoid bubble formation upstream the MF membrane. Pump flow rate was selected in order to cope with RO required feed flow rate.
P003 Centrifugal pump Fluid-o-Tech GA072 [RD7] to provide required flowrate and pressure to RO membrane.	A brushless pump was selected to avoid internal degradation due to possibly corrosive fluid. Stainless steel because of compatibility with the fluid. The pump can reach up to 10 bar which is max operative pressure of RO membrane. Flowrate compatible with RO membrane.
RO Pump Driver Moon's BLD10-A-S [RD8] for P003 Centrifugal pump Fluid-o-Tech GA072 [RD7].	The Driver regulates RO pump operating parameters.
P004 pump to feed the water quality monitoring subsystem (WUST and SWY LIBS) with a constant flowrate is needed. A peristaltic pump Etatron B3-V 1201 (PBV4337374) (24VDC) is used. [RD13]	Water is pumped in the water quality monitoring subsystem (WUST and SWY LIBS) at a constant flowrate from the reservoir.

2.2.3 Microfiltration Unit Design

Table 2-4: MF unit design features description and justification

Design Feature	Justification
MF unit uses a 0.45 micron pore size membrane to remove bacteria and solid particles.	Highest pore size that can remove bacteria and solid particles (req. 1.6.2 Potable Water Standard) limiting pressure drops and fast clogging of the filter. As per [RD1] , particles <2 µm are present in the system. Bacteria are not supposed to be in the system unless introduced by external contamination. 0.45 µm membrane at the beginning of the system prevents bacterial contamination and growth inside the system.
MF unit filter material is heterogeneous PES double layer.	PES is a hydrophilic material, compatible with water sample filtration. Asymmetric depth filter has an open matrix structure at their top, and a finer matrix structure towards the bottom. Gradient of porosity initially traps large particles and acts as a pre-filter increasing filter life and preventing clogging.
MF membrane contact area is 0.6 m ²	Oversized (TAS heritage) to prevent clogging
Sartorius Sartopore 2 Maxicaps size 1 0.45 µm 544-73-06-G-2-x-x-x [RD9]	COTS compatible with required flowrate (req. 2.4.4 WPS raw water processing characteristics) and lifetime (2.4.9 WPS lifetime performance) is chosen as microfiltration unit
MF unit positioned before RO unit	To prevent fouling and scaling of RO membrane that can occur because of recirculation and high water recovery.

2.2.4 Reverse Osmosis Unit Design

Table 2-5: RO unit design features description and justification

Design Feature	Justification
The Reverse Osmosis unit is used to remove inorganic contaminants.	To remove inorganics contaminants (especially ammonia) and salts present in raw water req. 2.4.3 WPS raw water composition.
Tap water reverse osmosis membrane is chosen to treat the TDS level in inlet water.	Tap water TDS concentration is, by definition, 100 – 300 mg/L, water coming from WECS TDS is <100 mg/L, this means that FilmTec Aqualast 1812-HR can treat WPS inlet water.
RO membrane is 1812 element	The name of the element 1812 refers to membrane dimensions: 18 means 1,8 inches (i.e. 45 mm) diameter membrane, 12 is the length of the membrane in inches (i.e. 300 mm). Dimensions are compatible with flowrates as the one required in WPS.
DUPONT FilmTec Aqualast 1812-HR [RD10]	Filmtech Aqualast membrane is chosen because of its salt rejection (99%) and its anti-scaling performance which leads to a long lifetime of the element.
Flat sheet configuration is chosen	Flat sheet configuration is preferred for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High Surface Area which allows for high flux rates and higher throughput in the system. • Can reduce fouling and prolong membrane life. • Can provide high-quality water with low levels of impurities.
RO concentrate is recirculated to feed tank	Recirculation of RO concentrate to feed tank is needed because of Req. 2.4.6 WPS allowable waste water, which requires water recovery >95% (section 2.2.8).
The concentrate is discharged in the brine tank when it is <5% of the feed water	Because of the low salinity of the inlet water, it is possible to highly concentrate the waste water (brine) in order to reach the >95% water recovery required.

2.2.5 Activated Carbon Unit Design

Table 2-6: AC unit design features description and justification

Design Feature	Justification
<p>Activated Carbon unit is used to remove organic contaminants.</p> <p>As a conservative assumption the AC unit is designed to remove 3 mg/L of methanol and 1 mg/L ethylene are considered [AD1].</p>	<p>Organic contaminants present in raw water as per req. 2.4.3, needs to be removed to reach composition in req. 1.6.3.</p>
<p>Granulated Activated Carbon Camel Carboclean Actisorb M.J. 950 as per [RD12]</p>	<p>Affinity with methanol evaluated for a better methanol removal.</p>
<p>AC unit is designed to treat at least 300 L before exhausting.</p> <p>The possibility to regenerate AC with water vapor is planned.</p>	<p>It is required in req. 2.4.9 WPS lifetime performance. For detailed volume calculation see section 2.2.5.a</p>
<p>AC unit bed configuration: minimum radius 2 [cm] and minimum volume 1 [L]</p>	<p>For choosing the dimensions of the bed, hydraulic considerations are done. See paragraph 2.2.5.b for details.</p>
<p>Final AC unit design:</p> <p><i>Final Volume:</i> $V = 1.0 +20\%/-0\%$ [L]</p> <p>According to carbon density [RD12], this volume corresponds to 470 [g] of activated carbons.</p>	<p>Volume and configuration calculated in section 2.2.6.a.</p> <p>The final dimensions are compatible with the dimensions calculated in sections 2.2.5.a and 2.2.5.b.</p>
<p>AC unit case is made in stainless steel.</p>	<p>AC unit was designed to be compatible with high temperatures in case of water vapor carbon regeneration.</p>

2.2.5.a Activated Carbon volume calculation

Contaminants concentration: $C_{MeOH} = 3$ [mg/L] ; $C_{Ethy} = 1$ [mg/L] ; $C_{Tot} = 3+1 = 4$ [mg/L]

Total Contaminants: $m_{org} = C_{Tot} * L_{Tot} = 4$ [mg/L] * 300 [L] = 1200 [mg]

Knowing the quantity that AC can adsorb related to the weight of AC (Carbon Loading), the total grams of AC needed can be calculated. For both ethylene and methanol the average value is 10% as a conservative assumption.

Carbon Loading Average: $m_{org} / m_c = 0.1$

Minimum Carbon Mass: $m_c = x / 0.1 = 12000$ [mg] = 12 [g]

Carbon Bulk Density: $D = 470$ [g/L]

Considering a 20% margin, the carbon volume is calculated.

Carbon Volume: $V_c = m_c / (0.80 * D) = 12$ [g] / $(0.80 * 470$ [g/L]) = 0.03 [L]

2.2.5.b Hydraulic considerations

Flowrate: $\dot{L} = 200 \text{ [mL/min]} = 0.2 \text{ [L/min]}$, equal to RO permeate flowrate [RD10]

For VOCs removal typical parameters of surface loading and empty contact bed time are:

Surface Loading: $SL = 200 \text{ [L/min/m}^2\text{]}$

EBCT: $EBCT = 5 \text{ [min]}$

Knowing these parameters, the minimum radius and volume can be calculated:

$$\text{Minimum Radius: } R_{\min} = \sqrt{\frac{\dot{L}}{SL * \pi}} = \sqrt{\frac{0.2 \left[\frac{L}{min}\right]}{200 \left[\frac{L}{min/m^2}\right] * \pi}} = 0.02 \text{ [m]} = 2 \text{ [cm]}$$

Minimum Volume: $V_{\min} = EBCT * \dot{L} = 5 \text{ [min]} * 0.2 \text{ [L/min]} = 1 \text{ [L]}$.

AC unit is able to treat water coming from WECS during integrated tests even if WECS supplies to WPS water with higher quantity of methanol because, calculating as in 2.2.5.a, 1 L of AC can treat till more than 100 mg/L of organic contaminants.

2.2.6 Ion Exchange Resins Unit Design

To design the ion exchange resins unit with an adequate margin considering the worst case, as inlet water is considered an ion concentration of 3.4 mEq/L which from TAS-I water treatment experience is the average ion quantity in contaminated water.

Table 2-7: Ion Exchange Resins unit design features description and justification

Design Feature	Justification
<p>The ion exchange resins unit is needed for final polishing of water, to reach the required conductivity level for required for electrolysis.</p> <p>As a conservative assumption ammonia ca. 1 mg/L and ca. 0.1 mg/L of other contaminants (sulfur dioxide, hydrogen sulfide, carbon dioxide) are considered [AD1].</p>	<p>Inorganic contaminants present in raw water as per req. 2.4.3, needs to be removed to reach composition in Req. 1.6.3.</p>
<p>AmberTec UP6040 H/OH [RD11] mixed bed ion exchange resins</p>	<p>Resins already space qualified and used in water treatment in space.</p>
<p>Ion exchange resins unit is designed to treat at least 300 L before exhausting.</p> <p>To design the ion exchange resins unit with an adequate margin considering the worst case, as inlet water is considered an ion concentration of 3.4 mEq/L which from TAS-I water treatment experience is the average ion quantity in contaminated water.</p>	<p>It is required in req. 2.4.9 WPS lifetime performance. For detailed volume calculation see section 2.2.6.a.</p>
<p>Final ion exchange resins unit design:</p> <p>The final volume considered for purchasing is $V = 1.1 +20\%/-0\%$ [L].</p> <p>According to resins density, this volume corresponds to 792 [g] of ion exchange resins.</p>	<p>Results coming from two design methods. It is demonstrated that the two methods used are in line. See sections 2.2.6.1 and 2.2.6.2 for details.</p>

2.2.6.a Ion Exchange Resins Volume

Anion removal capacity of 1.1 Eq/L, cation removal capacity of 2.0 Eq/L and density of 720 g/L are properties of Lenntech AmberTec UP6040.

Ion exchange resins unit is designed to treat 300 L ($L_{Tot} = 12$ L/h for 25 h) before regeneration.

Two design methods are used and compared.

2.2.6.1 Online calculator

The first design method used is the Lenntech online calculator.

As inputs for the calculator 3.4 mEq/L are used in anion section as Lenntech AmberTec UP6040 anion exchange capacity is lower than cation exchange capacity (worst case assumption) and 1 mg/L of ammonia, which corresponds to $5.9 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol/L and subsequently 1.06 mg/L of NH_4^+ .

Anions	MW g/mol	Concentration	unit	converted concentration	unit
NO ₃ ⁻	62.00		eq/L		eq/L
NO ₂ ⁻	46.01		eq/L		eq/L
Cl ⁻	35.45		eq/L		eq/L
SO ₄ ²⁻	98.06	3.4	meq/L	163.302	mg/L
HCO ₃ ⁻	61.02		eq/L		eq/L
F ⁻	19.00		eq/L		eq/L
TOTAL		0.0034	eq/L		

Cations	MW g/mol	Concentration	unit	converted concentration	unit
Na ⁺	22.99		eq/L		eq/L
K ⁺	39.10		eq/L		eq/L
Ca ²⁺	40.08		eq/L		eq/L
Mg ²⁺	24.31		eq/L		eq/L
NH ₄ ⁺	18.04	1.06	mg/L	0.05875831485587	meq/L
Mn ²⁺	54.94		eq/L		eq/L
TOTAL		0.00005875831	eq/L		

	Anion removal	Cation removal	
Exchange capacity	1.1	2	eq/L
Density Resin	0.72	0.72	kg/L
service flow	12		l/h
time between 2 regenerations (1 cycle)	25		hour(s)
Ions in water (1 cycle)	1.0199999999999999	0.01762749445676	eq/cycle
required-resin volume theoretical	0.9272727272727272	0.00881374722838	L/cycle
calculated mass of resin	0.6678363636363636	0.00634589800443	kg/cycle
Total required surface area	0.0009272727272727	0.00000881374722	m ²
Diameter Column	0.0344	0.00335	m

Figure 2-1: Ion Exchange unit online calculator data

The calculated volume is 0.94 L, a 20% margin is considered.

Real Volume: $V = V_{min} * 1.2 = 0.94 [L] * 1.2 = 1.1 [L]$

2.2.6.2 Calculation procedure

For the reasons explained in the previous paragraph, input ion concentration is approximated to $C_i = 3.4 + 0.06 = 3.46$ mEq/L (0,06 is the concentration in mEq/L of NH₄⁺ as it is shown in Figure 2-1). All the inputs parameters are listed at the beginning of the section.

At first it is calculated the ion load that the resins need to treat during resin life.

Initial Ion Load: $I = C_i * L_{Tot} = 3.46 [mEq/L] * 300 [L] = 1038 [mEq] = 1.038 [Eq]$

As a conservative assumption, all the load is considered anionic. The volume of resin needed to treat the ion load is calculated:

Minimum Volume: $V_{min} = I / \text{Anion Exchange Capacity} = 1.038 [Eq] / 1.1 [Eq/L] = 0.94 [L]$

A 20% margin is considered.

Real Volume: $V = V_{min} * 1.2 = 0.94 [L] * 1.2 = 1.1 [L]$

2.2.7 Consumables justification

Req. 2.4.8 WPS allowable consumables states that: The allowable consumables mass per kg recovered water shall not exceed 1g.

Consumables in WPS are activated carbon and ion exchange resins. At the moment, microfiltration is not considered as consumable because there is no data on life duration.

The breadboard as it is purchased is oversized for testing purposes and for cost containment as the units do not need to be customized.

It is possible to demonstrate with the following calculation that req. 2.4.8 is satisfied if the subsystem is not oversized.

The subsystem is designed to treat 300 L of raw water.

In section 2.2.5.a the minimum carbon volume for the required contaminant load is calculated. It results to be $V_{\min} = 0.03$ [L]. Considering that AC density is 470 [g/L] [RD12], the mass of AC required is 14.1 [g].

In section 2.2.6.a ion exchange resin volume is calculated considering 3.4 mEq/L of ionic load. This quantity is a conservative value for oversizing. The quantity of ammonia and salts present in the system before RO corresponds to 0.20 mEq/L. As the quantity of contaminants removed from RO is not tested, the complete ionic load before RO is considered for ion exchange resins design in this calculation.

Using the same procedure described in section 2.2.6.2 with 0.20 mEq/L, ion exchange resin volume needed is $V_{\min} = 0.25$ L. Considering that resin density is 720 [g/L] [RD11], the mass of resins required is 180 [g].

Considering these values, the total mass of consumables needed is 194.1 [g].

Grams of consumables per kg of recovered water is $194.1/300 = 0.65$.

2.2.8 Product Water to Feed Ratio Justification

Product water to feed ratio is required to be >95% (Req. 2.4.6 4 [AD1]). Water losses from the system are due to the discharge of RO concentrate.

To evaluate if it is possible to discharge maximum 5% of inlet water, the TDS level of concentrate solution is calculated and compared with RO membrane TDS working limits.

It is assumed that only inorganic compounds are retained by the RO membrane.

Considering 1.5L batch and a concentration of 1 mg/L of inorganic compounds (majority of ammonia), the inorganics quantity in the system is $1.5 \text{ [L]} * 1 \text{ [mg/L]} = 1.5 \text{ [mg]}$.

Sal rejection of the RO membrane is 99% [RD11], this means that in the concentrate $1.5 \text{ [mg]} * 0.99 = 1.49 \text{ [mg]}$ of inorganics are retained in the concentrate.

The maximum concentrate volume allowed is 5%: $1.5 \text{ [L]} * 0.05 = 0.075 \text{ [L]}$.

The concentration of inorganics in the concentrate is: $1.49 \text{ [mg]} / 0.075 \text{ [L]} = 19.8 \text{ [mg/L]}$.

Using this concentration, TDS of concentrate solution is calculated to be 21 [mg/L] (assuming 100% ammonia dissolved in NH_4^+ ions).

The RO membrane used, as described in section 2.2.4, is designed for tap water which, by definition, has TDS level $\approx 100 \text{ mg/L}$.

This means that RO membrane can work properly with concentrate TDS level if < 5% of the feed water is discharged.

2.2.9 Activated Carbon Steam Regeneration Option

An option evaluated to lower consumables of the subsystem is to regenerate activated carbon using steam, which can be produced by product water.

From literature [RD16] it is known that to regenerate activated carbons 3 to 5 kg of steam per kg of organic compound adsorbed are needed.

The quantity of steam needed to regenerate AC of WPS is calculated in order to evaluate the impact on water recovery.

In section 2.2.5.a it is calculated that the total mass of organics adsorbed is 1200 [mg] = 1.2 [g].

Considering the literature worst case (5 kg of steam per kg of organic), $1.2 * 5 = 6$ [g] of water are needed.

The AC unit is designed to treat 300 [L] of water before regeneration. This means that, considering product water to feed ratio equal to 95%, 6 [g] of water every 285 [kg] of product water are required for AC regeneration, which is an acceptable amount.

AC unit is designed in such a way that it is not expected to exhaust AC during the whole breadboard life. For this reason, WPS is set up to be upgraded with AC steam regeneration, but it is not implemented.

2.2.10 PCDH/Electrical Subsystem

The electrical subsystem of the LUWEX WPS BBM consists in direct connections between components (i.e. sensors and actuators) and connectors (interfaces). The PIN functions at subsystem level are reported in the following Table 2-8 and Table 2-9.

For detailed information on how to connect the LUWEX WPS subsystem with the LUWEX PCDH subsystem please refer to the PIN functions reported in Section 4.2.

Table 2-8: Sensors Connector PIN function

Component ID	Component Wires	PIN	Operating Voltage	Maximum Current
LIT01	Load cell transmitter 1 (+)	C	24VDC	50mA
	Load cell transmitter 1 (-)	D	24VDC	50mA
	Load cell 1 SIGNAL 4-20mA (SIG)	Y	4-20 mA	<0.1A
	Load cell 1 SIGNAL 4-20mA (GND)	Z	4-20 mA	<0.1A
LIT02	Load cell transmitter 2 (+)	H	24VDC	50mA
	Load cell transmitter 2 (-)	J	24VDC	50mA
	Load cell 2 SIGNAL 4-20mA (SIG)	b	4-20 mA	<0.1A
	Load cell 2 SIGNAL 4-20mA (GND)	c	4-20 mA	<0.1A
CIT01/CIT02	EC Sensor 1/2 (+)	w	24VDC	120mA
	EC Sensor 1/2 (-)	j	24VDC	120mA
	EC 1 (OUT)	v	4-20 mA	<0.1A
	EC 2 (OUT)	i	4-20 mA	<0.1A
FIT01/FIT02	Flowmeter 1/2 (+)	h	24VDC	160mA
	Flowmeter 1/2 (-)	S	24VDC	160mA
	Flow 1 (OUT)	T	4-20 mA	<0.1A
	Flow 2 (OUT)	U	4-20 mA	<0.1A
PIT01-PIT05	Pressure Sensor 1/2/3/4/5 (+)	e	24VDC	200mA
	Pressure 1 (OUT)	P	4-20 mA	<0.1A
	Pressure 2 (OUT)	f	4-20 mA	<0.1A
	Pressure 3 (OUT)	M	4-20 mA	<0.1A
	Pressure 4 (OUT)	g	4-20 mA	<0.1A
	Pressure 5 (OUT)	R	4-20 mA	<0.1A
TIT01	Temperature Sensor 1 (+)	s	24VDC	50mA
	Temperature 1 (OUT)	r	4-20 mA	<0.1A

Table 2-9: Actuators Connector PIN function

Component ID	Component Wires	PIN	Operating Voltage	Maximum Current
P001	Peristaltic Pump 1 (+)	A	24VDC	0.3A
	Peristaltic Pump 1 (-)	B	24VDC	0.3A
P002	Microfiltration Pump (+)	C	24VDC	5A
	Microfiltration Pump (-)	T	24VDC	5A
V004	3 ways, two position SV (+)	E	24VDC	0.5A
	3 ways, two position SV (-)	V	24VDC	0.5A
P003	RO Centrifugal Pump - DRIVER (+) – 1st	N	24VDC	5A
	RO Centrifugal Pump - DRIVER (+) – 2nd	M	24VDC	5A
	RO Centrifugal Pump - DRIVER (-) – 1st	a	24VDC	5A
	RO Centrifugal Pump - DRIVER (-) – 2nd	Z	24VDC	5A
	RO Centrifugal Pump - DRIVER (GND)	P	GND	-
	RO Centrifugal Pump - RS232 (RX)	J	RS232	<0.1A
	RO Centrifugal Pump - RS232 (TX)	H	RS232	<0.1A
	RO Centrifugal Pump - RS232 (GND)	X	RS232	<0.1A
P004	Peristaltic Pump 2 (+)	D	24VDC	0.3A
	Peristaltic Pump 2 (-)	U	24VDC	0.3A

Additionally, for laboratory and acceptance testing purposes, a dedicated WPS power, command and data handling subsystem is designed. The WPS PCDH module is schematically represented in Figure 2-2, in terms of electrical lines and components. It is ideally subdivided into six lines detailed as follow:

- L 1) Line 1 guarantees alimentation of the power supplies
- L 2) Line 2 provides power to PLC (power is decoupled between “controllers” and components)
- L 3) Line 3 provides power to the external components, either directly or through the relays set
- L 4) Line 4 guarantees communication between PLC and (1) components (AI channels), (2) USB & Ethernet HUB (via Ethernet cable), (3) relays set (DO channels)
- L 5) Line 5 provides communication between USB & Ethernet HUB and external components requiring RS232 protocols (including adapter cables RS232-to-USB)
- L 6) Line 6 provides power to the external components through the relays set

The as-built module is depicted in Figure 2-3.

Figure 2-2: WPS PCDH Schematic Electrical Lines

Figure 2-3: LUWEX PCDHM as-built

Design Feature	Justification
WPS operates at with DC power supply with voltages $\leq 28V$ (all components are powered at 24VDC)	As required Req. 2.4.11 [AD1].
The WPS control software is developed with LabVIEW 2017 SP1	As required in Req. 2.4.15 [AD1].

Design Feature	Justification
<p>Electrical subsystem components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mating connectors (male, plug) • PLC: NI Compact-RIO 9073 equipped with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Board 1: NI-9201 (AI-Voltage $\pm 10V$, 8 channels), NOT-USED ○ Board 2: NI-9203 (AI-Current 4-20mA, 8 channels) ○ Board 3: NI-9203 (AI-Current 4-20mA, 8 channels) ○ Board 4: NI-9472 (DO-relays, 8 channels) • USB & Ethernet HUB: StarTech, P/N: ST4300MINI • USB cable RS232-to-USB (for P003), P/N: USB-RS232-WE-1800-BT 5.0 • Power Supplies 24VDC (x3, total available 540W), consumption of approx. 450/500W (including PLC) • Finder relays (x5) • Safety switch (differential magneto-thermic), P/N: RS 221-1567 • Module's box, P/N: RS 775-5338 • Laboratory Laptop including necessary software 	<p>Components required to successfully control and power-up all WPS components</p>

2.3 P&ID with control loops

Figure 2-4: WPS P&ID with control loops

Table 2-10: Sensors and actuators functions

Design Feature	Justification
LIT01	Monitors water level in T001 and switches off the pumps if T001 is empty.
CIT01	Monitors conductivity level (i.e. salts and inorganic contaminants) of the water coming from T001.
PIT01/PIT02	Measure the pressure before and after MF unit and calculate the ΔP of the filter. When it overcome a certain set value, the filter needs to be changed.
FIT01	Measures permeate flux.
PIT03	Measures the pressure given from P003.
PIT04	Measures the pressure of the permeate after RO membrane.
CIT02	Monitors conductivity level (i.e. salts and inorganic contaminants) of the RO permeate to check the RO membrane performances.
PIT05	Measures the pressure of RO concentrate and sets V003 to recirculate the concentrate to T001 with adequate pressure.
TIT01	Monitors concentrate temperature to avoid $T > 50^\circ C$, max RO operating temperature. If T is too high, the pump needs to be stopped for a set period of time to lower T before recirculating concentrate to RO.
FIT02	Monitors the flux of concentrate to set the position of V003.
LIT02	Monitors water level in T003 and switches off the pumps if T003 is full.
V004	Discharges concentrate when the set value (volume <5% of inlet water volume) is reached.

2.4 Product tree and preliminary budgets

Table 2-11: WPS Product Tree

P&ID #	Element/Component	Qty	Manufacturer	p/n
Reservoirs				
T001	Raw water tank (2L)	1	Duran	21 801 63 57
T003	Clean water tank (2L)	1	Duran	21 801 63 57
T002	Waste water tank (0.5L)	1	Duran	21 801 44 59
Water Treatment Units				
F001	Microfiltration unit	1	Sartorius	Maxicaps size 1 544-73-06-G-2-x-x-x-
RO001	Reverse osmosis unit	1	DUPONT	Filmtech Aqualast 1812 HR
AC001	Activated carbon unit	1	Custom +TBD	Custom +TBD
R001	Ion exchange resin unit	1	Custom+DuPont	Custom + AmberTec UP6040 H/OH
Sensors and Controllers/Drivers				
FIT01/02	Flowmeter	2	IFM	SM6020
PIT01 to 5	Pressure sensor	5	IFM	PT5404
CIT01/02	Conductivity probe	2	IFM	LDL101
LIT01/02	Water tank level sensor (load cell)	2	P.I.ECO	Custom
TIT01	Temperature indicator	1	IFM	TA2105
Fluidic lines				
P003	RO pump (centrifugal)	1	Fluid-o-Tech	GA series
P003.1	RO Pump Driver	1	Moon's	BLD10-A-S
P002	Microfiltration pump	1	Marco Fluidtech	16404113-UPX-C (24VDC)
P001	WECS to WPS pump (peristaltic)	1	Etatron	B3-V 1201 PBV4337374
P004	WPS to SWY LIBS and WUST	1	Etatron	B3-V 1201 PBV4337374
V002/V005	Non Return Valves	2	John Guest	1/4SCV
V003	Regulation valve (needle)	1	TBD	TBD
V004	3 ways 2 positions solenoid valve	1	JP Fluid Control	TP-DA014S040F-024DC
	Piping set	1	John Guest	JGT1-4N
	Sampling port	5	John Guest	PPSV040808W
	Union Tee for Sampling ports	5	John Guest	PM0206E
	Inlet QD fitting male	1	Hamlet	QC4SSDL1/4
	Inlet QD fitting female	1	Hamlet	QC4SSBLB1/4
	QD fittings in line male	7	CPC	PLCD29004
	QD fittings in line male panel mounted	1	CPC	PLCD41004
	QD fittings in line female	8	CPC	PLCD11004
	Inlet I/F to + Outlet I/F from T001 male	4	CPC	PLCD29004
	Inlet I/F to + Outlet I/F from T001 female panel mounted	4	CPC	PLCD11004
	Inlet I/F to T002 male	1	CPC	PLCD29004
	Inlet I/F to T002 female panel mounted	1	CPC	PLCD11004
	Inlet I/F to + Outlet I/F from T003 male	4	CPC	PLCD29004
	Inlet I/F to + Outlet from T003 female panel mounted	4	CPC	PLCD11004
	Vacuum relief valves	3	The Lee Company	CLCP5510004S
Frame				
	Mounting plate	1	Custom	Custom
	Mounting brackets (1 set), handles (4x)	1	Bosch Rexroth	20 mm

Table 2-12: WPS mass and power budgets

P&ID #	Element/Component	Qty	Power per element	Total power - all on	Mass per element	Total Mass
-	-	-	(W)	(W)	(g)	(g)
Reservoirs						
T001	Raw water tank (2L)	1	-	-	1000	1000
T003	Clean water tank (2L)	1	-	-	1000	1000
T002	Waste water tank (0.5L)	1	-	-	500	500
Water Treatment Units						
F001	Microfiltration unit	1	-	-	300	300
RO001	Reverse osmosis unit	1	-	-	181	181
AC001	Activated carbon unit	1	-	-	3670	3670
R001	Ion exchange resin unit	1	-	-	3992	3992
Sensors and Controllers/Drivers						
FIT01/02	Flowmeter	2	1.92	3.84	717.2	1434.4
PIT01/02/03/04/05	Pressure sensor	5	1.68	8.4	59	295
CIT01/02	Conductivity probe	2	1.44	2.88	329.9	659.8
LIT01/02	Water tank level sensor (load cell)	2	1.2	2.4	1062	2124
TIT01	Temperature indicator	1	1.2	1.2	84	84
Fluidic lines						
P003	RO pump (centrifugal)	1	-	-	1417	1417
P003.1	RO Pump Driver	1	240	240	170	170
P002	Microfiltration pump	1	120	120	1400	1400
P001	WECS to WPS pump (peristaltic)	1	5	5	700	700
P004	WPS to SWY LIBS and WUST	1	5	5	700	700
V002/V005	Non Return Valves	2	-	-	30	60
V003	Regulation valve (needle)	1	-	-	280	280
V004	3 ways 2 positions solenoid valve	1	13	13	90	90
	Piping set	1	-	-	150	150
	Sampling port	5	-	-	15	75
	Union Tee for Sampling ports	5	-	-	10	50
	Inlet QD fitting male	1	-	-	20	20
	Inlet QD fitting female	1	-	-	20	20
	QD fittings in line male	7	-	-	10	70
	QD fittings in line male panel mounted	1	-	-	10	10
	QD fittings in line female	8	-	-	15	120
	Inlet I/F to + Outlet I/F from T001 male	4	-	-	10	40
	Inlet I/F to + Outlet I/F from T001 female panel mounted	4	-	-	15	60
	Inlet I/F to T002 male	1	-	-	10	10
	Inlet I/F to T002 female panel mounted	1	-	-	15	15
	Inlet I/F to + Outlet I/F from T003 male	4	-	-	10	40
	Inlet I/F to + Outlet from T003 female panel mounted	4	-	-	15	60
	Vacuum relief valves	3	-	-	15	45
Structure						
	Mounting plate	1	-	-	5500	5500
	Mounting brackets (1 set), handles (4x)	1	-	-	500	500
			Power		Mass	
			Subtotal (W)	401.7	Subtotal (g)	26842
			Margin (%)	10	Margin	
			Grand total (W)	441.2	Grand total (g)	26842

Table 2-13: WPS components design feature and justification

Design Feature	Justification
All the purchased components are CE compliant.	CE compliance is required in Req. 1.8.3 [AD1]
Total mass of the breadboard < 25 Kg excluding reservoirs and scales	As required in Req. 1.5.2 [AD1]

2.5 CAD drawings

WPS breadboard preliminary CAD drawing is presented in Figure 2-5, where it is represented the position of all the components inside WPS volume. Scales and reservoirs are not represented in the drawing because are placed outside this volume, on another rack level.

Figure 2-5: WPS and WPS RESERVOIRS 3D CAD drawing (ISO views)

Table 2-14: WPS dimensions design features definition and justification

Design Feature	Justification
WPS dimensions, excluding reservoirs and scales which are placed on a different level, are 700 mm x 440 mm x 400 mm.	As required in Req. 1.5.2 [AD1]

3 Procurement, integration and verification plan

All high level activities planned to be developed within WPS and PCDH procurement, integration and verification plan, are summarized in Table 3-1. Almost all relevant WPS components will be procured and assembled in full from a lower tier Supplier (P.I.ECO Lab Srl) hereinafter named “P.I.ECO”, having consolidated experience in equipment for space applications, including Advanced Closed Loop System (ACLS), installed onboard the ISS Columbus Module.

Acceptance Test campaign will be performed by the lower tier supplier, while the WPS Subsystem Functional verification tests will be performed c/o TAS-I Torino Premises.

Table 3-1: WPS MAIT high level task list

ID	Task Name	Task Type	Timeframe	Facility
100	WPS BBM COTS items purchase	Procurement	June – July 23	P.I.ECO Premises
101	Long lead Item + all needed ancillary items	Procurement	June – July 23	P.I.ECO Premises
102	Other components + all ancillary items	Procurement	June – July 23	P.I.ECO Premises
200	WPS BBM custom items manufacturing	Manufacturing	Ago - Sept 23	P.I.ECO Premises
201	Metal brackets manufacturing for WPS internal components fixing.	Manufacturing	Ago - Sept 23	P.I.ECO Premises
202	Primary structure + fixing supports manufacturing	Manufacturing	Ago - Sept 23	P.I.ECO Premises
300	WPS BBM assembly	Assembly	Ago - Sept 23	P.I.ECO Premises
301	Mechanical I/Fs installation on LM case.	Assembly	Ago - Sept 23	P.I.ECO Premises
302	WPS component mechanical fixing within WPS primary structure by means of previously manufactured brackets.	Assembly	Ago - Sept 23	P.I.ECO Premises
303	Electric subsystem assembly and all WPS active components cabling.	Assembly	Ago - Sept 23	P.I.ECO Premises
304	WPS pipelines assembly.	Assembly	Ago - Sept 23	P.I.ECO Premises
400	WPS Subsystem Acceptance Tests	Test	Sept 23	P.I.ECO Premises
401	Test A01 - Pin function verification	Test	Oct 23	P.I.ECO Premises
402	Test A02 - Mass and envelope verification	Test	Oct 23	P.I.ECO Premises + TAS-I
403	Test A03 - Leak check and flowrate verification	Test	Oct 23	P.I.ECO Premises + TAS-I
D1	WPS BBM module delivery to TAS	WPS Delivery	Nov 23	P.I.ECO to TAS-I
500	PCDH COTS items purchase	Procurement	July 23	TAS-I
600	PCDH custom items manufacturing	Manufacturing	July 23	TAS-I
700	PCDH assembly	Assembly	Sept 23	TAS-I
800	PCDH Acceptance Tests	Test	Sept 23	TAS-I
900	PCDH and scales integration with WPS	integration	Oct. 23	TAS-I
1000	WPS Subsystem Functional verification tests	Test	Oct. 23	TAS-I
1001	Test F01 - Outlet water parameters monitoring	Test	Oct. 23	TAS-I
1100	Detachment of PCDH from WPS	integration	Jan 24	TAS-I
D2	WPS subsystem delivery to TUBS	WPS Delivery	Feb 24	TAS-I to TUBS
1200	WPS subsystem integration within LUXWEX BBM	Integration	Mar 24	TUBS
1300	LUXWEX integrated system Performance verification test. See Chapter 4 of D3.1	Test	Mar – Apr 24	TUBS
1201	Complete system performances verification	Test	Apr 24	TUBS

Concerning the tasks proposed in Table 3-1, their performing approach is aimed at parallelizing the activities as much as possible, thereby minimizing the time required for the whole LUXWEX project execution.

In particular, all tasks detailed as per Table 3-1 have been organized to be carried out in parallel whenever possible, with possible overlaps, so as not to wait for the end of each task to start the next one.

Figure 3-1: WPS and PCDH MAIT flow

Figure 3-1 details WPS as well as PCDH MAIT activities logic, as previously described in Table 3-1.

3.1 WPS Subsystem Test Plan

Present paragraph provides a preliminary test plan involving all tests to be performed to close WPS Req. under TAS-I responsibility as per [AD1]. Such test plan focuses on all tests to be performed with the WPS HW at subsystem level. In contrast, all test planned to be performed at integrated breadboard level are detailed in [RD15]

WPS Subsystem Test Plan is split into two main areas based on each test purpose: WPS Subsystem acceptance tests to verify WPS HW manufacturing against design and WPS Subsystem Functional verification tests to verify design against functional performance, as well as any other constraints generated by the applicable Req. In particular:

- 1) WPS Subsystem acceptance test campaign will be performed at P.I.ECO Premises under TAS-I specification, detailing each test setup, test success criteria and high level step by step procedure.
- 2) WPS Subsystem Functional verification tests campaign will be performed at TAS-I Torino Premises within the Recyclab technological area.

Table 3-2 recalls all WPS requirements as per [AD1] to be closed by test and Table 3-3 details test Identification codes according to their typology. Table 3-4 lists all WPS Subsystem acceptance tests and WPS Subsystem Functional verification tests, including all the Req. closed by each of them.

Table 3-2: WPS requirements as per [AD1] to be closed by Test

Req. ID. as per D2.1	Req Title	Responsibility
1.5.2	WPS dimensions and mass	TAS
1.6.2	Potable water standard	TAS, WUST, SW
1.6.3	Water quality for electrolysis applications	TAS
1.7.1	Testing location	ALL
1.7.3	End-to-end system tests	ALL
2.4.4	WPS raw water processing characteristics	TAS
2.4.6	WPS allowable waste water	TAS
2.4.7	WPS product water physical characteristics	TAS
2.4.10	WPS processing parameters monitored	TAS

Table 3-3: Test Identification codes according to their typology

ID	Test Typology	HW configuration needed for verification
Axx	WPS Subsystem Acceptance Tests	WPS BBM only (subsystem level)
Fxx	WPS Subsystem Functional verification Tests	WPS BBM only (subsystem level)
2xx	LUXWEX integrated system Performance verification test (*)	WPS BBM integrated within the LUXWEX System

(*) See Chapter 4 of [RD15]

Table 3-4: WPS Subsystem Acceptance tests and WPS Subsystem Functional verification tests List

Test ID	Test Title	Affected Requirements as per D2.1	Test Start	Test End
WPS Subsystem Acceptance Tests				
A01	Pin function verification.	Test Added	27/09/23	28/09/23
A02	Mass and envelope verification.	• 1.5.2.	27/09/23	28/09/23
A03	Leak check and flowrate verification.	• 2.4.4, 2.4.7.	27/09/23	28/09/23
WPS Subsystem Functional verification tests				
F01	Outlet water parameters monitoring.	• 1.6.2, 1.6.3, 2.4.6, 2.4.10 (*)	2/10/23	31/10/23
LUXWEX integrated system Performance verification test (**)				
203	Complete system performances verification.	• 1.7.1, 1.7.3 • 1.6.2, 1.6.3, 1.7.2, 2.4.5, 2.4.6, 2.4.7, 2.4.10 (***)	See Chapter 4 of D3.1	See Chapter 4 of D3.1

Notes:

(*) Such Req. needs to be verified at both WPS subsystem and integrated LUXWEX breadboard level.

(**) See Chapter 4 of D3.1

(***) Req. 1.7.2, 2.4.5 and 2.4.7 are planned to be closed by performing test 203 “Complete system test”, at integrated LUXWEX Breadboard level.

3.2 Test A01: Pin function verification

3.2.1 Test Objective and Description

WPS pin function verification test is added to WPS acceptance test campaign due to the need to be compliant to standard safety practice, aimed at guaranteeing operator safety while also safeguarding HW functionalities. More in detail, the main objectives of present tests are summarized into the following steps:

- 1) Electrical continuity verification of “Sensors connector” and “Actuators connector”.
- 2) Functional verification of sensors and actuators when power operated one by one according to the proposed incremental approach.

This section refers to section 4.2 Electrical Interfaces for tables and figures

In particular, taking into account *Figure 4-3: Sensors Connector’s Layout and PIN allocation* and *Figure 4-4: Actuators Connector’s Layout and PIN allocation*, recalling both WPS “Sensors connector” and “Actuators connector” typology and pin allocation, the test is split into two main steps.

Step 01: Electrical continuity verification

Electrical continuity verification is performed by checking one by one all the pins according to both Table 4-4 for “Sensors connector” and Table 4-5 for “Actuators connector”.

Verification results concerning the electrical conduction of all sensors and actuators connector pins are recorded within a table listing components identifications, continuity (Y/N as possible outcomes) and functioning (Y/N as possible outcomes).

Step 02: Functional verification of sensors and actuators

After pin conduction verification, the expected working status of all sensors and actuators is checked by power operating one by one individually, according to the incremental approach detailed in configurations 01 to 10 as per Table 3-5.

Table 3-5: Sensors and Actuators functioning test configurations

LUXWEX	Active Components	Test Configurations									
ID		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Sensors											
LIT01 - LIT02	Scale 1/2	ON	ON	ON	ON	ON	ON	ON	ON	ON	ON
CIT01/ CIT02	EC Sensor	OFF	ON								
FIT01/ FIT02	Flowmeter	OFF	OFF	ON							
PIT01 - PIT05	Pressure Sensor 1 to 5	OFF	OFF	OFF	ON						
TIT01	Temperature Sensor	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	ON	ON	ON	ON	ON	ON
Actuators											
P001	Peristaltic Pump (+)	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	ON	ON	ON	ON	ON
P002	Microfiltration Pump (+)	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	ON	ON	ON	ON
V004	3 ways, 2 position SV (+)	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	ON	ON	ON
P003	RO Centrifugal Pump	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	ON	ON
P004	Peristaltic Pump (+)	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	ON
OUTCOMES:	S=Successful, NS= Not Successful	S/NS	S/NS	S/NS	S/NS	S/NS	S/NS	S/NS	S/NS	S/NS	S/NS

3.2.2 Test Equipment / Instrumentation and set-up

Pin function verification test needs to be performed on WPS before being integrated within the whole LUWEX BBM. For present test WPS is planned to be tested at module level on a work bench without the need to connect it with other LUWEX modules.

Setup planned for test steps 1 and 2 is detailed as follows:

- 1) Within Step 01, WPS is fully disconnected from any active component and the instrumentation used for electrical continuity verification covers the multimeter highlighted on ID. 01 of Table 3-6.
- 2) Within Step 02, PCDH is used as an external EGSE so as to provide the WPS with the needed electrical power. Inputs/outputs to/from WPS are managed by the PCDH, connected to WPS by means of both electrical I/Fs.

Table 3-6 - test support instrumentation/ tools/ materials list

ID	Name/ model	Manufact.	p/n	Unit of meas.	range	Accuracy
Instrumentation						
01	Fluke 287 True-RMS Electronics Logging Multimeter	Fluke Process Instruments	Fluke 287	[RD18]	[RD18]	[RD18]

3.2.3 Test Execution

Pin function verification is performed by checking electrical continuity on all the pins belonging to “Sensors connector” as per Table 2-8 and “Actuators connector” as per Table 2-9 by means of the multimeter detailed as per Table 3-6. Sensors and Actuators verification are performed according to the configurations as per Table 3-5, where also the functioning test outcome are detailed in the last raw.

3.2.4 Test Success Criteria

The functionalities to be checked as per section 3.2.1 are considered satisfied if all the conditions as per Table 3-7 are met:

Table 3-7: Pin function test success criteria according to test steps 01 and 02

Test Step	Success Criteria
01	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WPS sensors as well as actuators connectors typology complies with Figure 4-3 and Figure 4-4. • Continuity on each pin of “Sensors connector” as well as “Actuators connector” is checked, verified and marked as “Yes” in Table 4-4 and Table 4-5
02	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensors and actuators are able to be switched ON and OFF when power operated according to the configurations 01 to 10 as per Table 3-5.

3.3 Test A02: Mass and envelope verification

3.3.1 Test Objective and Description

Present test is aimed at verifying the following requirements as per [AD1].

- Req. 1.5.2

More in detail, the main objectives of present tests are:

- 1) To verify that WPS envelope, excluding storage units, is $\leq 700\text{mm} \times 440\text{mm} \times 400\text{mm}$.
- 2) To verify that WPS mass is ≤ 25 kg. Such value is calculated taking into account that following components are not to be considered within the overall WPS mass budget:
 - a. LIT01 Water tank level sensor (scale)
 - b. LIT02 Water tank level sensor (scale)
 - c. T001 Raw water tank (2L)
 - d. T003 Clean water tank (2L)

3.3.2 Test Equipment / Instrumentation and set-up

Present test is planned to be performed on WPS BBM before integration into the whole LUWEX system. For present test WPS BBM is tested at module level, on a work bench, without connecting it with other LUWEX modules. Test support instrumentation is presented in Table 3-8.

Table 3-8: Test support instrumentation/ tools/ materials list

ID	Name/ model	Manufact.	p/n	Unit of meas.	range	Accuracy
Instrumentation						
01	Measuring tape	RS PRO	848-7613	mm	0 to 1000	1
02	Weighting scale	KERN	NDE 150K50ip	kg	0 to 150	0.05

3.3.3 Test Execution

Present test is performed by collecting a set of n.10 measurements of WPS mass and, after that, n.10 length measurements, taken on axis “x”, “y” and “z” belonging to the reference system proposed for this test, according to Figure 3-2: WPS reference system.

Figure 3-2: WPS reference system

WPS Mass and Envelope measurement data are collected within a table with structure as per Table 3-9.

Table 3-9: WPS Mass and Envelope collected measurements

Measurement	WPS mass		WPS Envelope		
	-	X	Y	Z	
ID	kg	mm	mm	mm	mm
01	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW
02	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW
03	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW
04	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW
05	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW
06	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW
07	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW
08	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW
09	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW
10	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW
Average dimension	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW
Max allowable dimension	25	440	700	400	

3.3.4 Test Success Criteria

The functionalities to be checked as per section 3.3.1 are considered satisfied if all the conditions as per Table 3-10 are met:

Table 3-10: Mass and envelope verification test success criteria

ID	Success Criteria
01	WPS dimensions are ≤ 700mm x 440mm x 400mm
02	WPS mass is ≤ 25 kg. (without considering LIT01/02, and T001/003)

3.4 Test A03: Leak check and flowrate verification

3.4.1 Test Objective and Description

Present test is aimed at verifying the following requirements as per [AD1]:

- Req. 2.4.4
- Req. 2.4.7

More in detail, the main objectives of present tests are:

- 1) The verification that WPS is able to guarantee a flow rate >10 ml/min
- 2) The verification that no water leakages, hereinafter intended as water droplets, are observed by naked eye, neither escaping from WPS pipelines nor from any other WPS component.
- 3) The verification that when WPS receives water in the range 4 to 30 °C, the WPS outlet water is in the range 15 to 35°C.

3.4.2 Test Equipment / Instrumentation and set-up

Present test is planned to be performed on WPS BBM before integration into the whole LUWEX system. For present test WPS BBM is tested at module level, on a work bench, without connecting it with other LUWEX modules.

PCDH is used to provide the WPS with the needed electrical power as well as Inputs/outputs to/from WPS which is operated by a dedicated custom LabVIEW-based SW. Such SW is operated by an external laptop, connected to PCDH via Ethernet cable.

3.4.3 Test Execution

Leak check and flowrate verification is performed according to the following steps:

- 1) Actual water batch temperature is kept within the range 4 to 30°C.
- 2) WPS active components are switched ON.
- 3) Water is flown within WPS.
- 4) Actual WPS outlet water temperature is measured and recorded.
- 5) Time required for a complete batch to flow within WPS (water dwell time within WPS) is measured and recorded.
- 6) The actual flowrate from WPS to WUST and SWY LIBS subsystems is calculated by means of the amount of water delivered in a time frame of TBD seconds.
- 7) Actual and target flowrate are compared.
- 8) Actual and target WPS outlet water temperature are compared

3.4.4 Test Success Criteria

The functionalities to be checked as per section 3.4.1 are considered satisfied if all the conditions as per Table 3-11 are met:

Table 3-11 - Leak check and flowrate verification test success criteria

ID	Success Criteria
01	WPS can be operated in such a way to process water and to guarantee a flow rate > 10 ml/min
02	No water droplets are observed by naked eye on any WPS components surfaces.
03	The verification that when WPS receives water in the range 4 to 30 °C, the WPS outlet water is in the range 15 to 35°C.

3.5 Test F01: Outlet water parameters monitoring

3.5.1 Test Objective and Description

Present test is aimed at verifying the following requirements:

- Req. 1.6.2/ 1.6.3/ 2.4.6/ 2.4.10

All the above Req. needs to be closed also at LUXWEX integrated Breadboard level. This is planned to be performed as per Test 203 of D3.1 [RD15].

More in detail, the main objectives of present tests are:

- 1) To verify that WPS outlet water quality is compliant with the values as per Table 3-12.

Table 3-12: ASTM Standard Specification for high-purity water Type 1 and Type II [ASTM, 2017].

Parameters	Unit	Type I	Type II
Conductivity in (25°C)	µS·cm ⁻¹	< 0.056	< 1
Resistivity in (25°C)	MΩ·cm	> 18	> 1
TOC	µg·L ⁻¹	< 50	< 50

- 2) To verify that The WPS product water to feed ratio is >95%
- 3) To verify that WPS is able to monitor, by means of a LabVIEW-based SW, a set of product water parameters taking advantage of the sensors it is equipped with. Such monitoring covers the measurement of: temperature, pressure, flowrate and EC.

Taking into account all needed measurements, as per points 1 and 3, in addition to WPS's sensors, Recyclab laboratory instrumentation will be used for present test. This means that all measurements are split into two parts: a first subset

is performed by sensors that are on board WPS and the second subset is performed by Recyclab's laboratory instrumentation, according to Table 3-13

Table 3-13: ON and OFF line measurements according to the sensors used

Measurements	Sensors used	Monitored parameters
On line	Sensors installed onboard WPS, managed by PCDH via LabVIEW-based SW	Temp, Pressure, Flowrate, EC
Off line	Sensors that are part of TAS Recyclab Laboratory instrumentation	EC, pH, TOC

3.5.2 Test Equipment / Instrumentation and set-up

Outlet water parameters monitoring test needs to be performed on WPS before integration into the whole LUWEX System. For present test WPS is planned to be tested at module level on a work bench without the need to connect it with other LUWEX modules.

PCDH is used to provide the WPS with the needed electrical power as well as inputs/outputs to/from WPS which is operated by a dedicated custom LabVIEW-based SW. Such SW is operated by an external laptop, connected to PCDH via Ethernet cable.

In particular, a part from PCDH, all needed instrumentation is detailed in Table 3-14.

Table 3-14: test support instrumentation/ tools/ materials list

ID	Name/ model	Manufact.	p/n	Unit of meas.	range	Accuracy
“OFF line” measurements (Recyclab sensors)						
1	EC sensor (Recyclab)	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW
2	pH testing strips	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW
3	TOC sensor (Recyclab)	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW
“ON line” measurements (WPS sensors)						
1	Temperature indicator, TIT01	IFM	TA2105	TBW	TBW	TBW
2	Pressure sensors PIT03/04	IFM	PT5404	TBW	TBW	TBW
3	Flowmeters FIT01	IFM	SM6020	TBW	TBW	TBW
4	Conductivity probes CIT01/02	IFM	LDL101	TBW	TBW	TBW
Test support tools						
1	100 ml bottles for samples collection					
2	TOC vials (40ml)					

3.5.3 Test Execution

Outlet water parameters monitoring test is planned to be performed on n.8 different test waters. Composition of test waters is detailed in Table 3-15 while description and justification is detailed in Table 3-16.

N.3 purification runs for each test water composition are foreseen, i.e. 3 batches for each test water are treated one by one by WPS and submitted to parameters monitoring.

WPS water parameters are planned to be monitored during each WPS purification run.

Purification runs are planned to be 3, namely R1 to R3, since, by doing so, results amount concerning contaminants removal efficiency by means of each WPS technology is considered statistically significant.

Table 3-15: WPS test waters contained components, according to test waters composition ID

Test waters components	Test waters compositions ID (N.3 repetitions runs for each)							
	W1	W2	W3	W4	W5	W6	W7	W8
-								
Water	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Particulate	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
Methanol	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓
Ammonia	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓
Sulphur dioxide	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓

Table 3-16 Test waters typology, composition and justification

Water typology	Water composition	Justification why each water is tested
ID.	-	(n.3 runs foreseen)
W1	Deionized Water	To check eventual contamination of water by the system
W2	DI water and Particulate	To check the particulate removal efficiency of MF unit (and eventually other units onboard WPS).
W3	DI Water and Methanol (i.e. All organics present in raw water simulant)	To check the methanol removal efficiency of the single units (especially AC) and whether or not methanol removal occurs where expected in the system. Methanol is considered a critical contaminant in raw water.
W4	DI Water, Particulate and Sulfur Dioxide (i.e. inorganics except for Ammonia present in raw water simulant)	To check inorganics removal efficiency of the single units (especially RO and resins). At first inorganics are tested without ammonia, which is present in the highest amount, in raw water, to analyze better the behavior of the system.
W5	DI water and Ammonia	To check ammonia removal efficiency of the single units. Ammonia is considered as the most critical inorganic components of raw water solution. Ammonia is expected to be removed in RO unit.
W6	DI Water, Particulate, Ammonia and Sulfur Dioxide (i.e. All inorganics present in raw water simulant)	All inorganics compounds are tested together in raw water solution. The behavior with all inorganics together of RO and ion exchange resins is tested.
W7	Complete raw water simulant	Water is sampled after each technology is needed to evaluate technologies behavior toward the nominal composition of the solution.
W8	Complete raw water simulant	Only the outlet is tested for TOC, conductivity and pH TBC. The whole three runs are carried out as standard functioning of the subsystem. In these runs also water recovery is tested.

DLR which is responsible for Raw Water Simulants will supply TAS with concentrated solutions of test waters, whose typology W1 to W8 is detailed in Table 3-16. Starting from such concentrated solutions, TAS will prepare n.3 batches of 1500+/- 300 ml for each Test Water typology.

All samples are named according to the following ID: X-Y-Z, where:

- X = test water composition ID submitted to test (W1 to W8), according to Table 3-15.
- Y = purification run (R1 to R3) to which each test water composition ID is submitted.
- Z = sampling source from which water sample is collected, i.e.:
 - Sampling port number S1 to S5 for test water W1 to W7.
 - T003 for test water W8 only.

During WPS treatment, a total of n.108 samples are collected, in particular:

- For test water typology W1 to W7 and for each purification run R1 to R3, N.5 (90 ml) samples are collected, one from each sampling port, thus resulting in a total of n. 105 water samples (7x3x5).
- For test water typology W8, n.1 (90 ml) sample is collected from T003 for each purification run R1 to R3, thus resulting in a total of n.3 water samples.

After collection, the n.108 water samples are divided into two subset. In particular:

- 1) N.52 nominal water samples are collected and analyzed according to Table 3-19. In particular for each one of them, n.3 parameters are measured: EC, pH and TOC, thus resulting in 156 measurements (52x3). To do so, every sample is split into two parts so that:
 - a. 40 ml are poured in TOC analyzer vial and used for TOC measurements.
 - b. 50 ml are exploited for both EC and pH measurements.
- 2) N. 56 spare water samples are collected according to
- 3) Table 3-20, but measured only in case the planned measurements as per Table 3-19 shows unexpected results. In this case an additional amount of n.168 measurements are performed (56x3). To do so, every sample is split into two parts so that:
 - a. 40 ml are poured in TOC analyzer vial and used for TOC measurements.
 - b. 50 ml are exploited for both EC and pH measurements.

For clarification purposes, measurements amount to be performed according to test water, purification run ad needed monitored parameters are summarized in Table 3-17.

Table 3-17 Amount of measures foreseen for both nominal and spare samples

		Measurements amount for nominal samples				Measurements amount for spare samples			
		EC	pH	TOC	TOT	EC	pH	TOC	TOT
W1	R1	3	3	3	9	2	2	2	6
	R2	2	2	2	6	3	3	3	9
	R3	2	2	2	6	3	3	3	9
	TOT W1	7	7	7	21	8	8	8	24
W2	R1	3	3	3	9	2	2	2	6
	R2	2	2	2	6	3	3	3	9
	R3	2	2	2	6	3	3	3	9
	TOT W2	7	7	7	21	8	8	8	24
W3	R1	3	3	3	9	2	2	2	6
	R2	2	2	2	6	3	3	3	9
	R3	2	2	2	6	3	3	3	9
	TOT W3	7	7	7	21	8	8	8	24
W4	R1	3	3	3	9	2	2	2	6
	R2	2	2	2	6	3	3	3	9
	R3	2	2	2	6	3	3	3	9
	TOT W4	7	7	7	21	8	8	8	24
W5	R1	3	3	3	9	2	2	2	6
	R2	2	2	2	6	3	3	3	9
	R3	2	2	2	6	3	3	3	9
	TOT W5	7	7	7	21	8	8	8	24
W6	R1	3	3	3	9	2	2	2	6
	R2	2	2	2	6	3	3	3	9
	R3	2	2	2	6	3	3	3	9
	TOT W6	7	7	7	21	8	8	8	24
W7	R1	3	3	3	9	2	2	2	6
	R2	2	2	2	6	3	3	3	9
	R3	2	2	2	6	3	3	3	9
	TOT W7	7	7	7	21	8	8	8	24
W8	R1	1	1	1	3	-	-	-	-
	R2	1	1	1	3	-	-	-	-
	R3	1	1	1	3	-	-	-	-
	TOT W8	3	3	3	9				
Overall TOTAL		52	52	52	156	56	56	56	168

The overall outlet water parameters monitoring test logic is presented in Table 3-18.

Table 3-18: Test logic according to test water and purification run

Test water	Purification run	Procedure steps to be performed
W1	R1	1) Inlet water amount mass of Test water W-x in purification run R1 is measured before being flushed within WPS. 2) A set of n.5 90ml samples are collected while WPS treatment is ongoing, one from each WPS sampling port S1 to S5. 3) EC, pH and TOC are analyzed only on a limited set of samples, according to Table 3-19. 4) WPS onboard sensors are exploited to measure on line the following parameters: Temperature, Pressure, Flowrate and EC. 5) Outlet water amount mass of Batch_01 is measured after being flushed within WPS. 6) Product water to feed mass ratio is calculated and recorded. 7) OFF line measured data are reported in Table 3-19.
	R2	Repeat steps 1 to 7
	R3	Repeat steps 1 to 7
W2	R1 to R3	See Test Water W1, steps 1 to 7
W3	R1 to R3	See Test Water W1, steps 1 to 7
W4	R1 to R3	See Test Water W1, steps 1 to 7
W5	R1 to R3	See Test Water W1, steps 1 to 7
W6	R1 to R3	See Test Water W1, steps 1 to 7
W7	R1 to R3	See Test Water W1, steps 1 to 7
W8	R1	1) Inlet water amount mass of Test water_08 in purification run R1 is measured before being flushed within WPS. 2) WPS onboard sensors are exploited to measure on line the following parameters: Temperature, Pressure, Flowrate and EC. 3) Outlet water amount mass of Batch_01 is measured after being flushed within WPS. 4) Product water mass to feed mass ratio is calculated and recorded. 5) N.1 90ml sample is collected from T003 at the end of WPS treatment process and then analyzed off line in order to monitor EC, pH and TOC. 6) OFF line measured data are reported in Table 3-19.
	R2	Repeat steps 1 to 6
	R3	Repeat steps 1 to 6

Table 3-19: 52x nominal water samples ID planned for Test Water W1 to W8 (“OFF line” measurements)

Test Water	Purification Run	Water mass submitted to Purification Run		Water mass collected	Product to feed ratio	Param.	Unit of meas.	Sampling sources				
		Before WPS kg	After WPS kg					kg	kg	[-]	[-]	S1
W1	R1	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	μS/cm	W1-R1-S1	W1-R1-S3	W1-R1-S5	-	
						pH	-	W1-R1-S1	W1-R1-S3	W1-R1-S5	-	
						TOC	μg/L	W1-R1-S1	W1-R1-S3	W1-R1-S5	-	
	R2	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	μS/cm	-	W1-R2-S3	W1-R2-S5	-
							pH	-	-	W1-R2-S3	W1-R2-S5	-
							TOC	μg/L	-	W1-R2-S3	W1-R2-S5	-
	R3	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	μS/cm	-	W1-R3-S3	W1-R3-S5	-
							pH	-	-	W1-R3-S3	W1-R3-S5	-
							TOC	μg/L	-	W1-R3-S3	W1-R3-S5	-
W2	R1	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	μS/cm	W2-R1-S1	W2-R1-S3	W2-R1-S5	-	
						pH	-	W2-R1-S1	W2-R1-S3	W2-R1-S5	-	
						TOC	μg/L	W2-R1-S1	W2-R1-S3	W2-R1-S5	-	
	R2	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	μS/cm	-	W2-R2-S3	W2-R2-S5	-
							pH	-	-	W2-R2-S3	W2-R2-S5	-

Test Water	Purification Run	Water mass submitted to Purification Run	Water mass collected	Product to feed ratio	Pa-ram.	Unit of meas.	Sampling sources					
	R3	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TOC	µg/L	-	W2-R2-S3	W2-R2-S5	-	
						EC	µS/cm	-	W2-R3-S3	W2-R3-S5	-	
						pH	-	-	W2-R3-S3	W2-R3-S5	-	
						TOC	µg/L	-	W2-R3-S3	W2-R3-S5	-	
W3	R1	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	µS/cm	W3-R1-S1	W3-R1-S3	W3-R1-S5	-	
						pH	-	W3-R1-S1	W3-R1-S3	W3-R1-S5	-	
						TOC	µg/L	W3-R1-S1	W3-R1-S3	W3-R1-S5	-	
	R2	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	µS/cm	-	W3-R2-S3	W3-R2-S5	-
							pH	-	-	W3-R2-S3	W3-R2-S5	-
							TOC	µg/L	-	W3-R2-S3	W3-R2-S5	-
	R3	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	µS/cm	-	W3-R3-S3	W3-R3-S5	-
							pH	-	-	W3-R3-S3	W3-R3-S5	-
W4	R1	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	µS/cm	W4-R1-S1	W4-R1-S3	W4-R1-S5	-	
						pH	-	W4-R1-S1	W4-R1-S3	W4-R1-S5	-	
						TOC	µg/L	W4-R1-S1	W4-R1-S3	W4-R1-S5	-	
	R2	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	µS/cm	-	W4-R2-S3	W4-R2-S5	-
							pH	-	-	W4-R2-S3	W4-R2-S5	-
							TOC	µg/L	-	W4-R2-S3	W4-R2-S5	-
	R3	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	µS/cm	-	W4-R3-S3	W4-R3-S5	-
							pH	-	-	W4-R3-S3	W4-R3-S5	-
							TOC	µg/L	-	W4-R3-S3	W4-R3-S5	-
W5	R1	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	µS/cm	W5-R1-S1	W5-R1-S3	W5-R1-S5	-	
						pH	-	W5-R1-S1	W5-R1-S3	W5-R1-S5	-	
						TOC	µg/L	W5-R1-S1	W5-R1-S3	W5-R1-S5	-	
	R2	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	µS/cm	-	W5-R2-S3	W5-R2-S5	-
							pH	-	-	W5-R2-S3	W5-R2-S5	-
							TOC	µg/L	-	W5-R2-S3	W5-R2-S5	-
	R3	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	µS/cm	-	W5-R3-S3	W5-R3-S5	-
							pH	-	-	W5-R3-S3	W5-R3-S5	-
							TOC	µg/L	-	W5-R3-S3	W5-R3-S5	-
W6	R1	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	µS/cm	W6-R1-S1	W6-R1-S3	W6-R1-S5	-	
						pH	-	W6-R1-S1	W6-R1-S3	W6-R1-S5	-	
						TOC	µg/L	W6-R1-S1	W6-R1-S3	W6-R1-S5	-	
	R2	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	µS/cm	-	W6-R2-S3	W6-R2-S5	-
							pH	-	-	W6-R2-S3	W6-R2-S5	-
							TOC	µg/L	-	W6-R2-S3	W6-R2-S5	-
	R3	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	µS/cm	-	W6-R3-S3	W6-R3-S5	-
							pH	-	-	W6-R3-S3	W6-R3-S5	-
							TOC	µg/L	-	W6-R3-S3	W6-R3-S5	-
W7	R1	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	µS/cm	W7-R1-S1	W7-R1-S3	W7-R1-S5	-	
						pH	-	W7-R1-S1	W7-R1-S3	W7-R1-S5	-	
						TOC	µg/L	W7-R1-S1	W7-R1-S3	W7-R1-S5	-	
	R2	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	µS/cm	-	W7-R2-S3	W7-R2-S5	-
							pH	-	-	W7-R2-S3	W7-R2-S5	-
							TOC	µg/L	-	W7-R2-S3	W7-R2-S5	-
	R3	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	µS/cm	-	W7-R3-S3	W7-R3-S7	-
							pH	-	-	W7-R3-S3	W7-R3-S7	-
							TOC	µg/L	-	W7-R3-S3	W7-R3-S7	-
W8	R1	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	EC	µS/cm	-	-	-	W8-R1-T003	
						pH	-	-	-	-	W8-R1-T003	

Test Water	Purification Run	Water mass submitted to Purification Run	Water mass collected	Product to feed ratio	Param.	Unit of meas.	Sampling sources					
	R2	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TOC	µg/L	-	-	-	W8-R1-T003	
						EC	µS/cm	-	-	-	W8-R2-T003	
						pH	-	-	-	-	W8-R2-T003	
	R3	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TBW	TOC	µg/L	-	-	-	W8-R2-T003
							EC	µS/cm	-	-	-	W8-R3-T003
							pH	-	-	-	-	W8-R3-T003
							TOC	µg/L	-	-	-	W8-R3-T003
							EC	µS/cm	-	-	-	W8-R3-T003
							pH	-	-	-	-	W8-R3-T003

Table 3-20: 56x spare water samples ID planned for Test Water W1 to W7 to be collected, but measured only if deemed necessary (“OFF line” measurements)

Test Water	Purification Run	Param.	Unit of meas.	Sampling sources		
	ID	[-]	[-]	S1	S2	S4
W1	R1	EC	µS/cm	-	W1-R1-S2	W1-R1-S4
		pH	-	-	W1-R1-S2	W1-R1-S4
		TOC	µg/L	-	W1-R1-S2	W1-R1-S4
	R2	EC	µS/cm	W1-R2-S1	W1-R2-S2	W1-R2-S4
		pH	-	W1-R2-S1	W1-R2-S2	W1-R2-S4
		TOC	µg/L	W1-R2-S1	W1-R2-S2	W1-R2-S4
	R3	EC	µS/cm	W1-R3-S1	W1-R3-S2	W1-R3-S4
		pH	-	W1-R3-S1	W1-R3-S2	W1-R3-S4
		TOC	µg/L	W1-R3-S1	W1-R3-S2	W1-R3-S4
W2	R1	EC	µS/cm	-	W2-R1-S2	W2-R1-S4
		pH	-	-	W2-R1-S2	W2-R1-S4
		TOC	µg/L	-	W2-R1-S2	W2-R1-S4
	R2	EC	µS/cm	W2-R2-S1	W2-R2-S2	W2-R2-S4
		pH	-	W2-R2-S1	W2-R2-S2	W2-R2-S4
		TOC	µg/L	W2-R2-S1	W2-R2-S2	W2-R2-S4
	R3	EC	µS/cm	W2-R3-S1	W2-R3-S2	W2-R3-S4
		pH	-	W2-R3-S1	W2-R3-S2	W2-R3-S4
		TOC	µg/L	W2-R3-S1	W2-R3-S2	W2-R3-S4
W3	R1	EC	µS/cm	-	W3-R1-S2	W3-R1-S4
		pH	-	-	W3-R1-S2	W3-R1-S4
		TOC	µg/L	-	W3-R1-S2	W3-R1-S4
	R2	EC	µS/cm	W3-R2-S1	W3-R2-S2	W3-R2-S4
		pH	-	W3-R2-S1	W3-R2-S2	W3-R2-S4
		TOC	µg/L	W3-R2-S1	W3-R2-S2	W3-R2-S4
	R3	EC	µS/cm	W3-R3-S1	W3-R3-S2	W3-R3-S4
		pH	-	W3-R3-S1	W3-R3-S2	W3-R3-S4
		TOC	µg/L	W3-R3-S1	W3-R3-S2	W3-R3-S4
W4	R1	EC	µS/cm	-	W4-R1-S2	W4-R1-S4
		pH	-	-	W4-R1-S2	W4-R1-S4
		TOC	µg/L	-	W4-R1-S2	W4-R1-S4
	R2	EC	µS/cm	W4-R2-S1	W4-R2-S2	W4-R2-S4
		pH	-	W4-R2-S1	W4-R2-S2	W4-R2-S4
		TOC	µg/L	W4-R2-S1	W4-R2-S2	W4-R2-S4
	R3	EC	µS/cm	W4-R3-S1	W4-R3-S2	W4-R3-S4

Test Water	Purification Run	Param.	Unit of meas.	Sampling sources		
		pH	-	W4-R3-S1	W4-R3-S2	W4-R3-S4
		TOC	µg/L	W4-R3-S1	W4-R3-S2	W4-R3-S4
W5	R1	EC	µS/cm	-	W5-R1-S2	W5-R1-S4
		pH	-	-	W5-R1-S2	W5-R1-S4
		TOC	µg/L	-	W5-R1-S2	W5-R1-S4
	R2	EC	µS/cm	W5-R2-S1	W5-R2-S2	W5-R2-S4
		pH	-	W5-R2-S1	W5-R2-S2	W5-R2-S4
		TOC	µg/L	W5-R2-S1	W5-R2-S2	W5-R2-S4
	R3	EC	µS/cm	W5-R3-S1	W5-R3-S2	W5-R3-S4
		pH	-	W5-R3-S1	W5-R3-S2	W5-R3-S4
		TOC	µg/L	W5-R3-S1	W5-R3-S2	W5-R3-S4
W6	R1	EC	µS/cm	-	W6-R1-S2	W6-R1-S4
		pH	-	-	W6-R1-S2	W6-R1-S4
		TOC	µg/L	-	W6-R1-S2	W6-R1-S4
	R2	EC	µS/cm	W6-R2-S1	W6-R2-S2	W6-R2-S4
		pH	-	W6-R2-S1	W6-R2-S2	W6-R2-S4
		TOC	µg/L	W6-R2-S1	W6-R2-S2	W6-R2-S4
	R3	EC	µS/cm	W6-R3-S1	W6-R3-S2	W6-R3-S4
		pH	-	W6-R3-S1	W6-R3-S2	W6-R3-S4
		TOC	µg/L	W6-R3-S1	W6-R3-S2	W6-R3-S4
W7	R1	EC	µS/cm	-	W7-R1-S2	W7-R1-S4
		pH	-	-	W7-R1-S2	W7-R1-S4
		TOC	µg/L	-	W7-R1-S2	W7-R1-S4
	R2	EC	µS/cm	W7-R2-S1	W7-R2-S2	W7-R2-S4
		pH	-	W7-R2-S1	W7-R2-S2	W7-R2-S4
		TOC	µg/L	W7-R2-S1	W7-R2-S2	W7-R2-S4
	R3	EC	µS/cm	W7-R3-S1	W7-R3-S2	W7-R3-S4
		pH	-	W7-R3-S1	W7-R3-S2	W7-R3-S4
		TOC	µg/L	W7-R3-S1	W7-R3-S2	W7-R3-S4

3.5.4 Test Success Criteria

The functionalities to be checked as per section 3.5.1 are considered satisfied if all the conditions as per Table 3-21 are met:

Table 3-21: Outlet water parameters monitoring test success criteria

ID	Success Criteria
01	Water parameter monitoring is successfully performed according to sensors planned to be used as well as sampling ports/sources to be exploited as per Table 3-19 and Table 3-20
02	Outlet water EC and TOC are compliant to values as per Table 3-12
03	Product water mass to feed mass ratio is >95%

4 Interfaces between subsystems

4.1 Fluidic Interfaces

Figure 4-1: WPS fluidic interfaces P&ID

Figure 4-2: WPS front panel fluidic interfaces

Figure 4-1 shows the position of the interfaces inside WPS envelope, while Figure 4-2 highlights details the interfaces positioned on the WPS front panel, for easy access. In detail, sampling ports need to be accessible by the user, while the others fluidic and electrical interfaces are placed on the front panel to easily connect parts outside WPS envelope.

Table 4-1: WPS fluidic interfaces and fittings description

Interface	Type	Qty	Manufacturer	PN
CPCX.F	¼" CPC QD female self-locking fittings (Acetate)	8	CPC	PLCD11004
CPCX.M (except for CPC8.M)	¼" CPC QD male self-locking fittings (Acetate)	7	CPC	PLCD29004
CPC8.M	¼" CPC QD male self-locking fittings (Acetate) panel mounted	1	CPC	PLCD41004
SQD1.F	¼" female self-locking quick disconnect stainless steel fitting	1	Hamlet	QC4SSBLB1/4
SQD1.M	¼" male self-locking quick disconnect stainless steel fitting	1	Hamlet	QC4SSDL1/4
QDTX.F	¼" CPC QD female self-locking panel mounted fitting	5	CPC	PLCD11004
QDTX.M	¼" CPC QD male self-locking fittings	5	CPC	PLCD29004
F22.a	Sampling port, ¼" QD fitting shut-off valve	5	John Guest	PPSV040808W

Table 4-2: Interfaces and fittings design features description and justification

Design Feature	Justification
All CPCX.F + CPCX.M	All the fluidic interfaces inside the WPS subsystem are CPC self-locking QD (Req. 2.4.13 [AD1]) to simplify the connection and disconnection of units. As subsystem agreement, female part is positioned upstream and male counterpart is positioned downstream.
SQD1.F	Agreed with Water Extraction and Capturing Subsystem (male ¼" self-locking quick disconnect stainless steel fitting counterpart) for connection.
SQD1.M	At system level under Water Extraction and Capturing Subsystem responsibility. In the subsystem, during subsystem level test campaign, the fitting is needed to pour water from raw water solution bottle to T001.
CPC3.F - CPC3.M - CPC4.F - CPC4.M - CPC7.F - CPC7.M - CPC8.F - CPC8.M	A jumper is placed within these interfaces to guarantee the connection of the different units during test phase. The jumper would be useful in the optional event that some sensor of the Water Quality and Condition monitoring Subsystem is placed instead of the jumpers (although this is not the baseline). Responsibility of interfaces at system level described in D3.1 [RD15].
QDTX.F + QDTX.M	QD fittings, the female part is panel mounted on T001, T002 and T003 caps. The male counterparts connect WPS piping for water inlet to T001, T002 and T003 and water outlet from T001 and T003.
F22.a	Shut-off valves, allow sampling of water after each technology as required in [AD1] Req. 2.4.14.

4.2 Electrical Interfaces

The following Table 4-3 describes the WPS electrical interface at LUWEX system level. Connectors layout are depicted in Figure 4-3 and Figure 4-4, while the PIN functions are reported in Table 4-4 and Table 4-5.

Figure 4-5 shows the position of electrical interfaces on WPS subsystem.

Table 4-3: Electrical subsystem I/Fs

ID	Name	Description	Manu- fact.	PINs n.	P/N	Mating Connector (male)
01	Sensor Con- nector	Circular MIL STD D38999 female, panel mounted electric connector.	Souriau	41	8D0-21W41SN MIL STD: D38999/20WG41SN	8D5-21W41PN MIL STD: D38999/26WG41PN
02	Actuators Connector	Circular MIL STD D38999 female, panel mounted electric connector.	Souriau	26	8D0-17W26SN MIL STD: D38999/20WE26SN	8D5-17W26PN MIL STD: D38999/26WE26PN

Figure 4-3: Sensors Connector's Layout and PIN allocation

Figure 4-4: Actuators Connector's Layout and PIN allocation

Figure 4-5: WPS front panel electrical interfaces

Table 4-4: Sensors Connector PIN function

Component ID	Component Wires	PIN	PCDH Connection	Operating Voltage	Maximum Current
LIT01	Load cell transmitter 1 (+)	C	PS 24VDC (+)	24VDC	50mA
	Load cell transmitter 1 (-)	D	PS 24VDC (-)	24VDC	50mA
	Load cell 1 SIGNAL 4-20mA (SIG)	Y	AI Current - 01	4-20 mA	<0.1A
	Load cell 1 SIGNAL 4-20mA (GND)	Z	AI Current – GND/COM	4-20 mA	<0.1A
LIT02	Load cell transmitter 2 (+)	H	PS 24VDC (+)	24VDC	50mA
	Load cell transmitter 2 (-)	J	PS 24VDC (-)	24VDC	50mA
	Load cell 2 SIGNAL 4-20mA (SIG)	b	AI Current - 02	4-20 mA	<0.1A
	Load cell 2 SIGNAL 4-20mA (GND)	c	AI Current – GND/COM	4-20 mA	<0.1A
CIT01/CIT02	EC Sensor 1/2 (+)	w	PS 24VDC (+)	24VDC	120mA
	EC Sensor 1/2 (-)	j	PS 24VDC (-)	24VDC	120mA
	EC 1 (OUT)	v	AI Current - 03	4-20 mA	<0.1A
	EC 2 (OUT)	i	AI Current - 04	4-20 mA	<0.1A
FIT01/FIT02	Flowmeter 1/2 (+)	h	PS 24VDC (+)	24VDC	160mA
	Flowmeter 1/2 (-)	S	PS 24VDC (-)	24VDC	160mA
	Flow 1 (OUT)	T	AI Current - 05	4-20 mA	<0.1A
	Flow 2 (OUT)	U	AI Current - 06	4-20 mA	<0.1A
PIT01-PIT05*	Pressure Sensor 1/2/3/4/5 (+)	e	PS 24VDC (+)	24VDC	200mA
	Pressure 1 (OUT)	P	AI Current - 07	4-20 mA	<0.1A
	Pressure 2 (OUT)	f	AI Current - 08	4-20 mA	<0.1A
	Pressure 3 (OUT)	M	AI Current - 09	4-20 mA	<0.1A
	Pressure 4 (OUT)	g	AI Current - 10	4-20 mA	<0.1A
	Pressure 5 (OUT)	R	AI Current - 11	4-20 mA	<0.1A
TIT01*	Temperature Sensor 1 (+)	s	PS 24VDC (+)	24VDC	50mA
	Temperature 1 (OUT)	r	AI Current - 12	4-20 mA	<0.1A
-	SPARE	A B E G K p	-	-	-
-	NOT WIRED	N t a d X k m n q F L	-	-	-

***IMPORTANT NOTE:** PIT and TIT sensors are single-ended 4-20mA sensors, meaning that connections is guaranteed by connecting sensor positive leads to +24VDC and sensor output signals to acquisition PIN AI. In order to correctly read the sensor, the NI board’s COM PIN must be connected to the negative lead of the **same power supply** that power-up the sensors (-24VDC).

Table 4-5: Actuators Connector PIN function

Component ID	Component Wires	PIN	PCDH Connection	Operating Voltage	Maximum Current
P001	Peristaltic Pump 1 (+)	A	Relay 1	24VDC	0.3A
	Peristaltic Pump 1 (-)	B	PS 24VDC (-)	24VDC	0.3A
P002	Microfiltration Pump (+)	C	Relay 2	24VDC	5A
	Microfiltration Pump (-)	T	PS 24VDC (-)	24VDC	5A
V004	3 ways, two position SV (+)	E	Relay 3	24VDC	0.5A
	3 ways, two position SV (-)	V	PS 24VDC (-)	24VDC	0.5A
P003	RO Centrifugal Pump - DRIVER (+) – 1st	N	Relay 4	24VDC	5A
	RO Centrifugal Pump - DRIVER (+) – 2nd	M	Relay 4	24VDC	5A
	RO Centrifugal Pump - DRIVER (-) – 1st	a	PS 24VDC (-)	24VDC	5A
	RO Centrifugal Pump - DRIVER (-) – 2nd	Z	PS 24VDC (-)	24VDC	5A
	RO Centrifugal Pump - DRIVER (GND)	P	GND	GND	-
	RO Centrifugal Pump - RS232 (RX)	J	PC RS232 (TX)	RS232	<0.1A
	RO Centrifugal Pump - RS232 (TX)	H	PC RS232 (RX)	RS232	<0.1A
	RO Centrifugal Pump - RS232 (GND)	X	PC RS232 (GND)	RS232	<0.1A
P004	Peristaltic Pump 2 (+)	D	Relay 5	24VDC	0.3A
	Peristaltic Pump 2 (-)	U	PS 24VDC (-)	24VDC	0.3A
-	SPARE	G R S C F L	-	-	-
-	NOT WIRED	K W Y b	-	-	-

Design Feature	Justification
Electrical interfaces towards the system are D38999 MIL standard circular connector.	As required in Req. 2.4.12 [AD1].
<p>A total of 40 connections are required in order to properly connect the WPS system with the LUWEX PCDH (24 from sensors connector J3 and 16 from actuators connector J4), specifically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 12 AI channels (current readings, 4-20mA) plus 2 connections to the GND/COM PIN of the 4-20mA acquiring board • 6 connections to 5 relays powered by a 24VDC power supply (positive lead), 390W peak power consumption (<u>relay no. 4 requires a double connection to 2 connector's PINs</u>) • 6 connections to a 24VDC power supply (positive lead), 60W power consumption • 10 connections to a 24VDC power supply (negative leads) • 1 ground connection • 1 connection to 1 RS232 ports (3 wires) is required. This connection will be implemented via RS232-to-USB cables (P/N: USB-RS232-WE-1800-BT 5.0) and it will be directly connected to the experiment Laptop (or to an intermediate USB HUB) 	Connections required to successfully control and power-up all WPS components
<p>PIT and TIT sensors (x6 sensors) are single-ended 4-20mA sensors. Connections must follow the following scheme:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sensors' positive lead connected to Power Supply 1 positive lead (+24VDC) 2. Sensors' output signal (4-20mA) connected to correspondent NI board AI channel/PIN 3. Power Supply 1 negative lead (-24VDC) connected to NI board COM channel/PIN <p>In case the other sensors are powered with a Power Supply different than the Power Supply 1, the negative leads of both power supplies must be bridged together (NOTE: all sensors are powered at 24VDC therefore no voltage noise is foreseen)</p>	Connections required to successfully read and acquire sensors

4.3 Mechanical Interfaces

Present paragraph details WPS external mechanical I/Fs exploited for both, WPS structure and WPS connection to TUBS rack-like structure, which guarantees WPS configuration as part of the whole LUWEX System.

Figure 4-6 shows the position of the mechanical interfaces allocated for the subsystem structure (in green) and the interfaces allocated for WPS installation within TUBS 30mm Bosch Rexroth rack-like structure (in orange).

WPS components are constrained to the frame, needed to constrain also a 5 mm thick Polypropylene Copolymer (Moplen) plate with No. 4 handles, supported by aluminum alloy uprights, made from 20mm Bosch Rexroth profiles, each fixed to WPS frame with conic head screws.

Fluidic and electrical I/Fs are fixed on WPS frame front panel, made in 5 mm thick Polypropylene Copolymer (Moplen), showing a set of n.14 holes allocated for such purpose.

Figure 4-6: WPS mechanical interfaces (System level I/Fs in orange, Subsystem level I/Fs in green)

After the assembly, WPS is planned to be integrated within the TUBS 30mm Bosch Rexroth rack-like structure located in Braunschweig, Germany so as to be part of the whole LUWEX system. WPS configuration toward 30mm rack-like structure is presented in Figure 4-7. Fixing elements are steel M6 T-slot nuts that connect WPS plate to 30mm Bosh Rexroth longitudinal profiles.

Figure 4-7: WPS configuration toward TUBS Rack-like structure located in Braunschweig, Germany.

Table 4-6 provides the main details of all WPS mechanical I/Fs.

Table 4-6: WPS Mechanical I/F details

ID	Interface	Type	Qty	Supplier	p/n
01	I/F_M_01	Handles	4	Sugatsune	MJH-93
02	I/F_M_02	Stainless steel M6 T-slot nut, for 30mm profiles, 8mm scaling,	4	Bosch Rexroth	3842536602
03	I/F_M_03	Stainless steel hexagon socket screw, M6 x 16mm thread	4	RS PRO	281-114
04	I/F_M_04	Flat washer, Stainless Steel Smooth, for M6 screw/bolt, outer Ø 12mm, A2	4	RS PRO	527-404

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